

Oxidation of Aromatic Compounds by Potassium-Permanganate in presence of Acetic Anhydride

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Griehl's method has been applied to some aromatic compounds with interesting results.

W. Griehl¹ reported an interesting application of potassium permanganate as an oxidising agent in presence of acetic anhydride. He showed that naphthalene gave a good yield of 1-naphthaleneacetic acid. He extended this reaction to other aromatic compounds viz., 2-hydroxynaphthalene, anisole, diphenyl, α -propylbenzene and ethyl phenylacetate and obtained 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaleneacetic acid, 2-methoxyphenylacetic acid, *p*-diphenylacetic acid, 3, 4-diphenylhexane and α - α' -diphenyl succinic acid diethyl ester respectively. The formation of these compounds suggest that they are formed through acetylperoxide by a free radical mechanism. An application of this method for the preparation of 2,6-dimethoxyphenyl-acetic acid which is very difficult to obtain otherwise has already been reported by us². The present paper deals with oxidation of some more aromatic compounds.

Benzene, chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene did not react. Toluene gave no acidic product but a neutral steam volatile compound identified as dibenzyl. Similarly ethylbenzene and α -propylbenzene gave 2, 3-diphenylbutane and 3, 4-diphenylhexane as steam volatile products. Naphthalene and its derivatives except α -nitronaphthalene gave 1-naphthalene and substituted naphthalene-1-acetic acids. Anthracene and acenaphthene gave 1-anthraceneacetic acid and 5-acenaphtheneacetic acid respectively.

Benzene and naphthalene derivatives having methoxy groups as substituents gave good yields of substituted phenyl acetic acids and naphthaleneacetic acids. The orientation of acetic acid side chain in all the cases followed the general rules of orientation. 2-chloro-1-naphthaleneacetic acid and 2-bromo-1-naphthalene-acetic acids are new compounds. The results are summarised in table I. The extension of this reaction containing both methoxy and alkyl group will be reported in a subsequent paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure.—The aromatic compound (25 g.) and acetic anhydride (150 ml) were taken in a two-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser. It was heated to boiling and finely powdered potassium permanganate (3 g.) was added in small lots in the course of 20 min.

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2. Jayamma, Inamdar and Nargund, *Chem. Sci.*, 1958, **27**, 170.

Each addition brought about a vigorous reaction. When the addition was over, excess of acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was steam distilled to remove acetic acid, excess of starting material and the reaction product if steam volatile. The residue was extracted with a hot solution of sodium bicarbonate, filtered and the filtrate acidified. The precipitate was collected and purified by crystallisation. The identity of the compounds was proved by mixed melting point and analysis.

TABLE I

Compound (25 g.) oxidised	Compound recovered	Yield of oxidation product and m.p.
Toluene	17 g	1.0 g. dibenzyl ³ , m.p. 51-52°
Ethylbenzene	21 g	0.5 g. 2,3-diphenylbutane ⁴ , m.p. 128°
n-propylbenzene	15 g	4.0 g. 3,4-diphenylhexane ⁵ , m.p. 90°
1-methoxynaphthalene	20 g	3.5 g. 4-methoxy-1-naphthalene acetic acid ⁶ , m.p. 144°
2-methoxynaphthalene	17 g	5.5 g. 2-methoxy-1-naphthaleneacetic acid ⁶ , m.p. 210°
1-chloronaphthalene	17 g.	5.0 g. 4-chloro-1-naphthaleneacetic acid ⁶ , m.p. 171°
2-chloronaphthalene	18 g	2.4 g. 2-chloro-1-naphthaleneacetic acid, m.p. 150° (Found Cl, 15.9; C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ .Cl requires Cl, 16.1%)
1-Bromonaphthalene	17 g	5.0 g. 4-bromo-1-naphthaleneacetic acid ⁶ , m.p. 173°
2-Bromonaphthalene	18 g	2.7 g. 2-bromo-1-naphthaleneacetic acid, m.p. 145° (Found: Br. 30.3; C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ .Br. requires Br 30.1%)
Anthracene	21 g	1.59 g. 1-anthraceneacetic acid ⁷ , m.p. 187°
Acenaphthene	20 g	5.0 g. 5-acenaphtheneacetic acid ⁸ , m.p. 174°
Hydroquinone dimethyl ether	20 g.	1.5 g. 2,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid ⁹ , m.p. 124°
Veratrole	18 g.	2.0 g. 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid ¹⁰ , m.p. 95°

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